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Surface Reaction on Alumina Catalyst.

Synthesis of 6-Nitrocholest-3,5-diene in Dry Media

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BASIC alumina has been successfully employed for the preparation of dienolic esters from β -allenic esters in good yield with high stereospecificity^{1,2}. We report here a simple method for the preparation of 6-nitrocholest-3,5-diene (4), a versatile intermediate for the synthesis of steroidal compounds. 3 β -Hydroxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1)³ and its 3 β -acetoxy (2)⁴ and 3 β -tosyloxy (3)⁵ analogues when allowed to stand over a column of basic alumina provided 6-nitrocholest-3,5-diene (4) in quantitative yield. The elimination of tosyloxy group in 3 seems to be faster as compared to acetoxy or hydroxyl group in 2 and 1, respectively. A probable mechanism of alumina catalysed elimination has been suggested (Scheme 1).

Experimental

IR spectra (nujol) were recorded on Pye-Unicam sp-300 spectrophotometer, and nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian A-60 instrument with Me₄Si as the internal standard. Tlc plates were coated with silica gel. A 20% aqueous solution of perchloric acid was used as spraying agent, anhydrous sodium sulphate used as the drying agent; and weakly basic alumina (200-300 mesh) for column chromatography was used after being dried at 200-300° in muffle furnace.

6-Nitrocholesta-3,5-diene (4): (a) A solution of 3 β -hydroxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1.0 g) dissolved in dry ether (20 ml) was adsorbed over basic alumina (20 g). The residual ether was removed under reduced pressure and the reaction mixture kept at room temperature for 48 h. Elution with ether yielded a semisolid mass which on crystallisation from methanol afforded 6-nitrocholesta-3,5-diene (4) as yellowish crystals (900 mg, 90%), m.p. 72° (lit⁶ 72-3°) (Found: C, 78.42; H, 10.21; N, 3.25. C₂₇H₄₄NO₂ (M⁺.413) required: C, 78.45; H,

- 1, R=OH
- 2, R=OAc
- 3, R=OTs

R' = H, Ac, Ts

Scheme 1

10.41; N, 3.38%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 690 (C=C-C=C-NO₂), 1 515 and 1 350 cm⁻¹ (C-NO₂); δ 6.5d (J 10Hz, C₄-H), 6.0m (C₆-H), 1.0 (C₁₀-CH₃), 0.70 (C₁₈-CH₃), 0.95 and 0.83 (remaining CH₃).

Under similar reaction conditions, 3 β -acetoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (2) and 3 β -tosyloxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (3) afforded 4 in 91 and 93% yields, respectively.

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